

LOVING THE COUNTRY IS FAITHFUL

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6951028>

Abstract. This article emphasizes the greatness of Motherland. On the initiative of President Shavkat Mirziyoyev's "Vatandoshlar" public fund was established. The purpose of the fund is to develop a sense of patriotism in the hearts of our compatriots living abroad and in our country, it was noted that the role of culture of our nation is enormous.

Keywords: homeland, Motherland, fund, nation, culture, traditions.

ЛЮБИТЬ СТРАНУ ЕСТЬ ВЕРНОСТЬ

Аннотация. В этой статье подчеркивается величие Родины. По инициативе Президента Шавката Мирзиёева был создан общественный фонд «Ватандошлар». Целью фонда является воспитание чувства патриотизма в сердцах наших соотечественников, проживающих за рубежом и в нашей стране, отмечалось, что роль культуры нашего народа огромна.

Ключевые слова: дом, Родина, фонд, нация, культура, традиции.

INTRODUCTION

"The homeland is the shrine of my soul"

Abdul Rauf Fitrat

Homeland is a great word. Homeland is a concept that means the place of birth, the motherland, the place where people live, the place of birth and upbringing of their ancestors, the territory, the social environment, and the country. The concept of the homeland has changed, expanded, and developed over the centuries with the environment of socio-economic development. In ancient times, the place where a particular tribe lived was considered his homeland. The nation was formed from the union of blood and language tribes. The place where the people lived was called nationality. The phrase "Chanbil Eli" is also used in the Uzbek folk epic Alpomish".

With the emergence of central government within a certain territory, the word "homeland" began to mean the concepts of people and state. With the rise of the language, customs, culture, spirituality, and economic and social life of the people, a commonality was formed between the people.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The Republic of Uzbekistan is the homeland of all people living in this land, regardless of nationality, language, or religion. This means that the people of Uzbekistan, regardless of nationality, are citizens of the Republic of Uzbekistan, which is enshrined in Article 8 of our Constitution. In this case, the people, the state, and the homeland have the same meaning. By the Republic of Uzbekistan, we mean the homeland, by the homeland we mean the Republic of Uzbekistan.

During the former dictatorial regime, the ruling ideology tried to falsify the concept of a homeland for us and instill in our hearts and minds the concept of an abstract homeland. For Uzbeks, places they had never been to in their lives, thousands of kilometers away, did not grow cocaine, and did not see the sun for months, seemed to be the homeland along with Uzbekistan. However, the homeland is a historically formed concept. Independence is a real sense of

homeland in the minds and consciousness of our people, which strengthens the notions of the motherland. Today, loving and respecting one's motherland, maintaining the inviolability of its borders, selflessly serving to enhance its honor, and educating the younger generation in the spirit of love and devotion to the motherland are becoming truly honorable deeds.

RESULTS

On August 11, 2021, on the initiative of President Shavkat Mirziyoyev Miromonovich, the Public Fund "Vatandoshlar" was established. Under Resolution PQ-5220. The main purpose of the establishment of this public fund "Vatandoshlar" - more than 10 million citizens living in nearly 100 countries around the world to support more than 170 cultural centers established by them.

The main activities of the Public Fund "Vatandoshlar" are:

- Cooperation and development of relations with compatriots living and working abroad and public associations established by them, as well as assistance in the protection of their rights and freedoms;
- Toto provides material and moral support to our compatriots in difficult situations in foreign countries and provides legal assistance in terms of information.
- Supporting the Uzbek language in foreign countries, activities aimed at preserving and developing the culture, customs, traditions, and national values of our people;
- Promotion and popularization of the rich scientific, spiritual and cultural heritage of our country in foreign countries, assistance to compatriots in organizing cultural and educational events;
- To support the scientific, creative research and activities of scientists and artists living and working in developed countries, aimed at enhancing the prestige and prestige of our country;
- Assistance in ensuring the participation of famous writers and poets, scientists, religious scholars, representatives of culture and art, and our athletes in prestigious events organized by our compatriots in foreign countries;
- Involvement of our compatriots living and working in foreign countries in entrepreneurship, investment, scientific, educational, and cultural activities in Uzbekistan;
- Launch of an interactive electronic portal aimed at providing our compatriots living abroad with information about the rich history, culture, political and socio-economic life of Uzbekistan
- Issues such as creating opportunities for our compatriots living and working abroad to study higher education in the Uzbek language, culture, cinema, and art on an equal footing with the citizens of the Republic.

DISCUSSION

We are a nation with a very rich past and culture. In the IX-XII centuries In the IX-XII centuries, The first period of the Renaissance (Renesas) was in our region. Our country has produced scientists who have made a significant contribution to world culture and development.

The creation of the science of algebra was the creation of the work of our great compatriot al-Khwarizmi "Al-Jaber Val muqabala". Al-Khwarizmi's discoveries are at the heart of the creation of our convenient smartphone, which we carry in our ordinary pockets. Az-Zamakhshari, who grew up in Khorezm, went to Arabia and created Arabic grammar, which is a great contribution to world civilization. Today, we study the Qur'an through Az-Zamahshari's

Al-Kashshaf, which is a great honor for us. Abu Rayhan al-Biruni was one of the first to determine that the earth was round, and five centuries before Columbus, he logically predicted the existence of the Americas. In addition, our scholars, such as al-Farabi, Ibn Sina, and Al-Bukhari, contributed to the development of religion. Our scholars, such as Al-Hakim at-Termizi, and Isa Termizi, also made a great contribution to world civilization in the IX-XII centuries.

I would like to emphasize that the culture of the XIV-XVI centuries of the Timurids had a great impact on the development of our country and the world. Only Amir Temur should be consulted and acted in the management of the Sultanate in the "Temur Tuzuk" so that you will not regret it in the end." It is not difficult to learn from these two words how the great master Amir Temur ruled the great kingdom. Amir Temur was also a patron of science, culture, architecture, and art. The research of Amir Temur's grandson Mirzo Ulugbek in astronomy was a world-class discovery for the world culture and civilization of that time. In 1428-1429 Mirzo Ulugbek built an observatory in Samarkand. This observatory has a huge sextant. At the observatory, scientists such as Qazizoda Rumi, Jamshid Giyosiddin al-Kashi, and Ali Kushchi studied celestial bodies. At that time, no other place in the world had such a large instrument for observing celestial bodies. Ulugbek also built madrasas in Samarkand, Bukhara, and Gijduvan, these madrasas, which were built by him, served as the university of that time. In addition, in the XV-XVI centuries, such great thinkers as Alisher Navoi, and Zahiriddin Muhammad Babur lived and worked, and they also made a great contribution to world culture and civilization.

CONCLUSIONS

To conclude, I would like to say that the great people named above were true patriots. They devoted all their energy and enthusiasm to their homeland. I have only mentioned some great patriots, and many such great patriots have left our country. Referring to something above, the role of the culture of our nation is great in the study of the scientific heritage of such great patriots, in conveying them to our compatriots living in our country and abroad, and in developing a sense of patriotism.

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